

NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION IN THE PROCESS OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION**Marika Sherazadishvili***Doctor of Philology, Professor of Gori State University,
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ORCID-0000-0002-2500-6252***Abstract**

Communication is a fundamental concept and phenomenon that has been essential for human existence, and not only, since time immemorial. Communication is a relationship, and life is based on these relationships. The entire culture of humanity may be considered as one great communication, the centre of which is a human being. A personality is formed through communication; it means nothing in isolation. A person is valued specifically by the scope of their influence and authority, that is, by the sort of power that each of us possesses to a greater or lesser degree and establishes it through relationships.

The purpose of the paper is to show that although communication primarily involves verbal communication, non-verbal communication also plays an equally important role in this process, especially in interactions between people with different cultural experiences. The signs and means of non-verbal communication are different, or the same sign is perceived differently in different cultures, that is why it becomes a source of a number of misunderstandings and problems. In order to avoid this, it is necessary to study and research these differences across different cultures.

Intercultural misunderstandings are the source of a number of problems. If we do not understand cultural diversity, do not master the skills to interact effectively with people who are completely different from us, or do not have the desire to do so, our world will significantly worsen.

Keywords: Intercultural communication, culture, interaction, verbal communication, non-verbal communication.

Introduction: Intercultural communication involves direct interaction between representatives of different cultures. It is easy to imagine how difficult this relationship might be between people with different cultural experiences who have little in common.

The importance of non-verbal communication in intercultural studies and the need to study it were seen by the famous American anthropologist Edward Hall. He wrote the book "The Silent Language"; 20% of the book is devoted to non-verbal communication. The book discusses the issues "What is culture?", "Time Talks", "Space Speaks", etc. We will discuss the signs of non-verbal communication that are common to all cultures and facilitate communication between representatives of different cultures.

As a rule, citizens of different countries are more different from each other than people of the same country. What distinguishes one country from another is called a national culture. A child acquires it from the birth. Whether we like it or not, we often interact with people from other countries - we travel and host tourists, we study with foreigners and study abroad, we work in multi-ethnic organisations; people all over the world are connected to each other through knowledge, religions, ideologies, weapons, money, illness, trade, sports.

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worsen. According to Albert Mehrabian, a professor at the University of California (UCLA), the share of verbal information in the communication process is only 7%. The remaining 93% is non-verbal information, of which 38% is the voice tone and intonation, and 55% is a body language - gestures, facial expressions, body movements, etc. We generally have free control over verbal communication, or speech. The situation is different with non-verbal communication. It is not dependent on the conscious mind and its change occurs subconsciously. It is important that these two ways of communication match each other. If they do not, things are going badly. They are telling us one thing, thinking another, and their subconscious is giving them away. Similar to the unconscious use of grammatical rules, a person follows the unwritten rules of non-verbal behaviour and unconsciously acquires them along with mastering their native language. Identification with one's own societal representatives serves as one of its core mechanisms. Mastering a foreign language in its fullest form involves mastering the system of non-verbal means characteristic of that culture.

Discussion and results: In different countries and cultures, means of expressing "body language" are perceived differently. For example, nodding the head is seen as a sign of agreement in the West, although it can have many different meanings in different countries around the world and does not necessarily always mean "yes".

Eye contact is considered rude in Japan. They mostly look down, at their shoes, or in the air. Despite the various body languages in different countries, there

is a common language, recognising by which we understand what kind of person we are dealing with, whether they enjoy interacting with us, etc.

1. If a person holds objects directly in front of their body, such as a coffee cup, handbag, and similar objects, this person is shy and reserved, and their actions indicate that they are hiding behind objects. Therefore, to hide these weaknesses, we need to keep the things beside ourselves.

2. Checking your watch frequently is a clear sign of boredom, especially if you are talking to someone.

3. Touching the face, especially the nose, while talking is a widely recognized sign of lying. Also, when covering the mouth with a hand, the speaker is most often lying.

4. Another clear sign of a lie is an artificial smile. A genuine smile reaches the corners of the eyes and changes the entire expression of the face. While a fake smile involves only the mouth and lips. It is quite easy to tell the difference between the two.

5. A hands akimbo posture is usually used to express arrogance and pride.

6. When we do not look the speaker directly, it indicates that we do not enjoy interacting with them, or that we are not interested in what they are saying, etc.

As we can see, body language is the phenomenon that can convey the most about a person's feelings and emotions without verbal expression. That is why it is important to know at least the small details that will help us conduct a business meeting or a simple conversation in a positive way.

Broadly, gestures serve five following functions: Symbol, illustration, adaptation, regulator, and indication of an emotion. We need to assume that these functions are characterised by more or less national and cultural specificity and their discussion primarily involves the differentiation of non-verbal means of communication. Basic communication gestures are shared universally across cultures. When people are happy, they smile, when they are sad, they frown, and when they are angry, they have an angry expression.

In the US, the UK, Australia, and New Zealand, a thumb up might be used for hitchhiking. It can be used in another sense to express that everything is fine. In Greece, this gesture means "shut up". Imagine an American who tries to stop a car on the roads of Greece with this gesture.

What are the signals that indicate someone agrees with us?

In almost all cultures, there are several indicators by which we can conclude that others accept our suggestions and agree with us: They place their hands on the table in an outstretched position, their palms are open, they nod their heads, they smile often, and they unbutton their jackets/coats. This is an indicator of friendship and willingness to cooperate with you, etc.

It is also important to understand whether people are interested in what we are talking about. We might waste our time. There are several gestures, movements, etc., based on which we can conclude that the speaker is interested in what we are talking about:

a) Maintains eye contact for more than 60% of the entire interaction,

b) The wider the eyes are opened, the greater is the interest. In general, people maintain eye contact longer when listening than when speaking,

c) They maintain a straight head position and nod to confirm agreement, showing they are fully attentive,

d) The foot is directed toward the speaker,

e) They smile often. But, it is worth noting that a prolonged smile is not genuine. It demonstrates courtesy, but not friendliness.

However, only a few nonverbal communication signals can be considered universal and equally accepted in all countries or cultures, while most of them have multiple meanings, and what is accepted in one culture, or in one country, might be completely unacceptable and even offensive in another. For example:

- Waving the index finger to call someone - the "come here" gesture. In our country, this is a completely harmless gesture, however, in a number of cultures it is perceived as rude, and in some places even obscene. In the Middle East, Portugal, Spain, Latin America, Japan, Indonesia and Hong Kong, it is better to wave to someone with all your fingers or your entire hand (the palm should be faced down).

- Pointing the finger at another person. While this gesture is perceived as simple rudeness in our country, it is completely unacceptable in many other cultures. In the countries of the Middle and Far East, an outstretched hand is used for this purpose, while in Indonesia, the thumb is used.

- Smile. This gesture is universal, however, different cultures have different reasons for smiling. For example, Japanese people smile when they are angry or confused. In other Asian countries, people smile, for example, when they feel embarrassed. In the US, smiling is one of the most important means of communication. The Americans smile not only when meeting and greeting anyone, but also when making eye contact with a complete stranger. In other countries, people "save" their smiles for closer people and friends.

- Eye contact. In Western culture, moderate eye contact is both acceptable and desirable. However, in some other cultures (Asian and Eastern countries), children are taught from a young age to minimize eye contact, especially when talking to adults (in the broad sense of the word), because staring into the eyes is perceived as arrogance and insolence. In the case of interaction between representatives of these two different cultures, a lack of eye contact (gazing away) may be perceived, at best, as passive aggression.

- The showing the sole of the shoe. In many cultures, especially in Asia and the East, showing the soles of your shoes - the dirtiest and lowest part of your body - is considered disrespectful.

- Showing the "OK" sign with your fingers. In many countries, this meaning remains unchanged, although in Brazil and Germany, this gesture is considered obscene. In Japan it is used to mean "money", in France it has the additional meaning of "zero" or "useless".

- In Japan, it is very offensive to pass something with one hand. Even something as small as a pencil should be handed over with both hands. In some other

Eastern countries, it is not allowed to hand over something with the left hand because the left hand is considered "unclean".

- In Georgia, it is common for men to kiss each other when meeting. In the US, this kind of thing only happens between homosexuals.

- The familiar nodding of the head up and down as a sign of agreement is a seemingly universal gesture, however, in Bulgaria and Greece it has a completely opposite meaning and refers to "no". Also, nodding may be more a sign of affirmation rather than agreement in some cultures. This gesture may say, "Yes, I am listening to you carefully," rather than "Yes, I understand what you are saying and I agree with you". So nodding your head might mean, "I hear you, but I disagree".

As to proxemics, another mean of expressing non-verbal communication, the fact of the existence of so-called distant and contact nations is commonly used to demonstrate the difference in the spatial arrangement of proxemic or communication members. The first group includes Northern Europe, the USA, the contact group includes Southern Europe, Asia Minor, and Latin America. In relationships between North Americans and Latin Americans, the former try to protect their personal space (up to 70 cm), while the latter try to establish relationships at a shorter distance. For example, Arabs like to stand close and hold the speaker, which puts Northern Europeans in an awkward position.

Americans feel insecure in Arab homes because the feeling of large spaces irritates them. Arab homes are twice as large as American homes. Social behaviour also differs between Western and Arab cultures.

Touching with a hand is allowed in public places in Arabia. However, this is not an expression of rudeness, as Americans believe. In the Western world, especially in Northern Europe, touching a person's body or clothing is not acceptable. In France, touching someone without reason can be considered as an assault. There is also a difference concerning the distance. It is acceptable for Arabs to be at close distance when speaking. The American manner of talking from one room to another, or maintaining a professional distance, is considered rude and cold. An Arab diplomat felt humiliated in an American hospital because a nurse kept a certain distance from him. One Arab even asked, "Do I smell bad?" Or are you afraid of me? A steady gaze into the eyes, a touch with the hand, and the feeling of someone else's breath while talking are unusual for Europeans, while it is acceptable for Arabs. Apart from distinguishing between contact and distant nations, the entire system of non-verbal means can be categorised into two types: Cultures where context plays a greater or lesser role. A highly contextual culture is characterised by placing great importance on non-verbal signals. Such are Japanese and Arabic cultures, where great importance is attached to traditional gestures and postures. Less contextual cultures (German, North American) give more importance to words, and traditional forms

of communication are used less. Contact between representatives of these two different cultures often leads to mutual dissatisfaction. An American finds it difficult to communicate with a Japanese person because he does not understand the unspoken intentions of the Japanese; while a Japanese person, on the contrary, believes that an intelligent person should understand the meaning of a conversation from the context.

When talking about non-verbal communication, it is impossible not to mention a phenomenon that emerged at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries - silent cinema. Silent film actors had a perfect grasp of the basics of the body language, because for them it was the only way to bring their on-screen faces to life. At that time, the best actors were considered those with rich facial expressions and expressive body language, so actors devoted considerable time to studying pantomime and ballet. When silent films were replaced by sound films and less attention was paid to the non-verbal aspects of acting, the old actors were replaced by actors with good verbal abilities.

Conclusions: Intercultural misunderstandings are the source of a number of problems. If we do not understand cultural diversity, do not master the skills to interact effectively with people who are completely different from us, or do not have the desire to do so, our world will significantly worsen. In addition, intercultural (cross-cultural) communication is a source of enrichment for our own experience, it will help us to see things that we take for granted in a different light.

The importance of non-verbal communication in the process of intercultural communication and, in general, intercultural research is great. We see that each gesture, facial expression, posture, etc. might have different meanings in each culture, so in order to establish effective communication with representatives of other cultures, it is necessary to study their non-verbal speech in addition to verbal.

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